
Sensitive Data & Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) Repository Lifecycle Factors

FAIR IMPACT Use Case CESSDA/UKDS: PIDS for Sensitive Data

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Introduction

This list¹ of factors for consideration focuses on sensitive data handling from the perspective of the repository phase of the digital object lifecycle. The sensitive data in scope includes, but is not limited to, sensitive personal data² and could include digital objects that are sensitive for e.g. commercial, cultural or ecological reasons. However, the primary purpose is to support Social Science data handling through the FAIR IMPACT³ work on persistent identifiers⁴, specifically the UK Data Service⁵ and CESSDA Use Case on Sensitive Data⁶.

To provide sufficient context this includes factors that are relevant beyond sensitive data, but it prioritises activities and functions that may imply a change to digital objects' data and/or metadata with a consequent change to their sensitivity status. The events and intervention points imply a need to update provenance information and, depending on local practice, may imply a new persistent identifier with an update to the version and change log information, or an update to a version and change log information under the current persistent identifier. This focus means that otherwise important criteria such as secure custody transfer and storage are not addressed.

Lifecycle Perspective

The lifecycle activities and functions used to structure this document are based on an aggregated crosswalk across a number of repository requirements, criteria and standards⁷.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19348263>

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https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/legal-grounds-processing-data/sensitive-data/what-personal-data-considered-sensitive_en

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/wp3-persistent-identifiers>

⁵ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

⁶ Change triggers impacting PID generation for sensitive data within the Social Sciences

⁷ L'Hours, H., Bell, D., & Parkes, O. (2026). Metadata and Data Services Activities and Functions - MaDSAF. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19348676>

Conceive, Create, Collect (Pre-Repository)

This working paper focuses on factors relevant during the repository phase of the digital object lifecycle. However, the list of items for consideration by the repository at deposit informs possible actions in the pre-repository phase. From the point of project conception and funding negotiation, through to the creation and collection of data and metadata, many repositories maintain a relationship with researchers, including providing guidance and training. Good practices during this phase add quality and reduce complexity for the rest of the lifecycle.

Deposit & Appraisal

Does the digital object being offered to the repository for deposit have:

1. Predefined terms and conditions, licences or other rights related information
2. One or more persistent identifiers already assigned to one or more parts of the object
3. A pre-existing provenance history of custody and change
4. A clear object model (data, metadata and associated documentation) for the deposit
5. An associated version model for defining how the identifiers have been assigned and the terms by which they, or associated metadata, would be changed in response to changes in the object
6. A pre-existing assessment of the digital objects' sensitivity

Some or all of these factors may be included in a data management plan.

If the digital object is deemed acceptable for deposit during the appraisal process, the repository should consider whether it has the resources, people and expertise to deliver the level of care (retention, curation, preservation etc.) required for the period of time initially required. This should include appropriate secure handling of sensitive data and appropriate rights to undertake the services offered.

The repository should further evaluate:

1. Predefined terms and conditions, licences or other rights related information
 - a. **Whether these are compatible with the terms of deposit and rights required by the repository, including rights to be passed on to data reusers.**
2. One or more persistent identifiers already assigned to one or more parts of the object
 - a. **Whether the existing PID approach will be continued, or replaced by one set by the repository with a link to any previously assigned identifiers.**
3. A pre-existing provenance history of custody and change
 - a. **How the pre-deposit provenance and history will be retained and communicated to end users.**

For digital objects that are part of a longitudinal study and/or series of related data collection events it may be necessary to align information across several digital objects, e.g. to ensure variables through multiple waves of statistical data are compatible.

For sensitive digital objects there are additional considerations. The sensitivity level of the object will influence what metadata can be shared for discovery, and how the digital object can be accessed and reused.

During curation the object may be changed, or derived objects may be created that differ from the original. In all these cases, the sensitivity of the digital object could increase, decrease or stay the same.

Directly identifiable personal information may be:

- Anonymised (deleting personally identifiable information)
- Pseudonymised (replacing personal identifiers but retaining a 'key' for re-identification)

Other curation actions may:

- Remove specific types of information entirely
- Reduce the granularity of information (e.g. removing more detailed geographical information or grouping data points such as age)

Each case may affect the assessed sensitivity level of the object and therefore the rights (permissions, prohibitions, duties) associated with the resultant objects that in turn influence.

- Permitted access routes, methods and persons
- Permitted reuse purposes and environments

Each scenario is a change whose justification, timing, responsible parties and outcomes should be recorded through provenance metadata. These changes include the possible deletion of sensitive versions of digital objects and their replacement by non-sensitive versions. Secure deletion of prior versions becomes part of the provenance history of the digital object.

The current and future level of care⁸ to be provided for the digital object (data and metadata) will also be relevant to the approach to copies, versions and identifiers. This includes whether additional instances of digital objects are created in different formats for access and preservation, the preparation of metadata to comply with different schemas, and the enrichment of metadata to enable understanding and reuse.

⁸ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

Throughout the deposit and curation phases, each copy of a digital object must be clearly identified and each managed change subject to a clear version strategy⁹.

Discovery & Identification

The assignment of persistent identifiers is a necessary precursor to releasing digital objects' metadata to support resource discovery by end users.

Resource discovery metadata used in open access environments must be a subset of the non-sensitive metadata that the repository has the right to share.

Digital objects' metadata should provide links to previous and subsequent versions, and their differences should be documented.

The repository approach to version management should be clear to end users, including what sort of changes would imply a new persistent identifier and what may instead be recorded through a 'change log'.

The rights information provided with the digital object should be sufficient to ensure appropriate protection (e.g. sensitivity level), to enable access and to guide reuse.

Access

The complexities of managing access to digital objects can increase as the data and metadata become more sensitive. For instance, an approach based on the 5 Safes¹⁰ could restrict access based on intended use (Safe Projects) that is approved by data owners for the public good, and on assurances that researchers are trained and authorised (Safe People).

ReUse

Repositories that provide access to open data as files that can be used on a researchers' local computer may simply approve for download and ensure that the licence conditions for reuse are clear.

For sensitive data, a repository or other service may be responsible for mediating the environments where digital objects are reused. As well as providing secure remote access or safe rooms (Safe Settings in 5 Safes terms) the results of research may need to be screened and approved to ensure they are non-disclosive before they can be released (Safe Outputs).

Researchers working with secure environments may undertake analyses on whole digital objects, subsets of data or on the results of linkages between multiple source datasets. As

⁹ Repository-internal identification and versioning strategies are beyond the immediate scope of this working paper; instead, the focus is on identifiers and version information to support discovery, access, re-use and citation by end-users.

¹⁰ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

for the curation phase above each object derived from subsetting and linkage may be subject to internal identification and version strategies.

The scope of this paper applies to the case that a derived digital object may need to be persistently identified outside the reuse environment. This would apply to outputs that have been approved as non-disclosive and released, but also to digital objects within the secure reuse environment as they may need to be cited, even if they cannot be accessed.

For each changed or derived digital object created during mediated re-use there may be a need to reappraise for retention, curation or preservation e.g. so the creator knows it will be retained or actively preserved for reuse by themselves or another researcher.

As federated analytics and more computational methods (like machine learning) become more common in social science research, other digital objects associated with data in the secure reuse environments may also need to be managed and persistently identified by the repository. For example, in federated analytics the code, as well the version of the data the script was run on, would be essential in any scientific replication of that research. Other digital objects which may not be able to leave the secure reuse environment due to disclosure risk (like machine learning models) may also need to be managed and identified by the repository if they are to be cited in research and reused - either by the model's creator or new researchers, and on the original data or on new data.

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